

Communicating uncertainty about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID: protocol for a randomized trial

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Background

Public health messaging matters – it shapes how people understand important health risks and what can be done to mitigate them. Ideally such communications are evidence-based – but even the best communications can fail if messaging is executed poorly, as has been seen during the COVID epidemic.¹

Decision scientists have articulated basic principles for effective health communication, for example using simple and familiar wording, clear visual design, presenting, structured comparisons of alternatives, and careful testing in the target audiences.²⁻⁴

A recent randomized trial assessed the effect of these principles on communication effectiveness in the context of COVID-19 home test kit instructions, using a real example.⁵ The trial showed that individuals randomized to instructions that did not follow best decision science principles (the actual FDA-authorized instructions) vs. those that did (carefully pre-tested intervention instructions) were more likely to fail to quarantine appropriately (33% vs. 14% failed; 95%CI for the 19% difference, 6%to 31%).

Evidence from randomized trials documents the importance of both the format and content of health messaging. *Formatting* examples include how use of percentages (e.g., 10%) vs. frequency formats (e.g., 10 in 100) can improve comprehension⁶, how absolute vs. relative risk measures for communicating treatment effects are better understood^{3,7} and help people make decisions more consistent with their values⁸

Content examples include the importance of presenting both benefits and harms when describing interventions⁹, and highlighting study limitations such as how simple nondirective explanations about surrogate outcomes and newly approved drugs enhance evidence-based decision making about prescription drugs.¹⁰

There is also evidence supporting the importance of communication about the uncertainty of research findings in both the professional literature,¹¹⁻¹⁴ and in plain language summaries for the public.¹⁵ This includes both statistical uncertainty (i.e., imprecision)¹⁴ and the overall uncertainty, due to the risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias.^{11,13} However there are still open questions about the best formats and language for presenting both kinds of uncertainty, and how people understand and react to such information.

A recent pair of trials¹⁶ found that including “quality cues” in communications tempered the public’s tendency to assume that quality of evidence presented without such cues is high (when it was not), and reporting that evidence quality was low decreased trust, perception of intervention efficacy, and likelihood of adopting it. However, the formats used to communicate uncertainty in the trial differed only by a single word: “certainty of evidence” vs. “quality of evidence”.

The certainty of the evidence can affect the decisions that people make. If the purpose of a message is to inform people rather than to persuade them,¹⁷ it is necessary to include information about the certainty of the evidence. Not doing so can be misleading.

We propose to set up a health messages laboratory (lab) to enhance the quality of public health messaging (**Appendix 1**). The focus of the messages will be on the effects of public health and social measures to prevent and control infectious disease outbreaks, and evaluations of the effects of those messages. The lab will promote best practices in message development (i.e., attending to the foregoing communication principles and evidence) and facilitate user testing (**Appendix 2**) and

randomized trials assessing the effects of public health messages on the publics’ understanding of the messages, beliefs, decisions, and behaviours.

The present study is designed as a proof-of-concept exercise to develop and test a communication meant to summarize the results of a recent randomized trial examining the effects of wearing glasses on the chance of developing COVID-19.¹⁸ This project will allow us to refine the development of key components of the health messages lab and gain new knowledge about the effects of alternative formats to communicate uncertainty on participants beliefs, decisions, and behaviours.

Objectives

The objectives of this randomized trial are:

- To compare the effects of three ways of communicating the overall uncertainty of the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID and
- To compare the effects of including the margin of error (confidence interval) compared to not including it.

The primary outcome for all 6 summary versions tested is understanding of the uncertainty.

For the 3 summary versions that include the margin of error (compared to those that do not), there is an additional co-primary outcome, assessing understanding of statistical uncertainty (i.e., precision of the effect estimates).

Methods

Trial design

We will conduct an online, parallel group, individually randomized, pragmatic trial using a 3x2 factorial design (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Factorial design

Margin of error (confidence interval)	Overall uncertainty		
	“GRADE” language*	“Colloquial” language†	None
Yes	“GRADE” + margin of error	“Colloquial” + margin of error	No overall uncertainty +margin of error
No	“GRADE” -margin of error	“Colloquial” -margin of error	No overall uncertainty -margin of error

* Based on the Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care Group’s guidance for communicating the certainty of evidence based on the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach to assessing the certainty of evidence¹²

† A less formal expression of the overall uncertainty language used in ordinary or familiar conversation, corresponding to the same GRADE assessment of the certainty of the evidence

Recruitment of participants

To compare the functionality, data quality, and efficiency of online recruitment platforms, we will recruit participants through 2 online platforms: Survey Monkey Audience and Prolific (**Appendix 1**). To be eligible, participants must be ≥ 18 years old, literate in Norwegian or English, and currently reside in Norway or the United States. We will exclude individuals who regularly wear any kind of glasses (i.e., prescription or sunglasses) all or most of the time, using a screener question prior to randomization.

We will use features of each of the platforms to screen for bots and fraudulent participants (**Table 2**).

Table 2. Data quality features for Prolific and Survey Monkey Audience.

Platform	Features
Prolific ¹⁹	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Requiring non-VOIP phone numbers and IDs to verify participant accounts• Verifying participant IP/ISP quality• Ensuring each participant has a unique payment account (i.e., PayPal, Circle)• Bot detection• Real-time monitoring of participant usage patterns• Attention and Comprehension Check ²⁰
Survey Monkey Audience ²¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use of a charitable incentive model• Bot and fraud detection• A double-opt-in system for participants to reduce professional survey taking• Response quality tools using metadata to detect speeding, and filtering or deleting responses• Randomization of the order in which response options appear²²

Randomization

Eligible participants will be randomized in equal numbers to one of the six groups shown in **Table 1**, using the methods provided by each of the platforms. All participants will be asked to read a scenario introducing the idea of wearing glasses to reduce COVID risk:

Imagine you hear that glasses may reduce your chance of becoming infected with COVID. You go online to find out more information and find a website that says...

They will then be shown one of six plain language summaries (in English or Norwegian) of the results of the recent randomized trial of the effects of wearing glasses on the chance of developing COVID-19, ^{Error! Bookmark not defined.} according to their randomized group (**Table 1**).

Interventions

The six versions of the summary to which participants will be allocated are shown in **Appendix 3**. The version using “colloquial” language for the overall certainty and including the margin of error” is shown in **Figure 1**. The yellow highlighted text differs across the three versions of communicating the overall uncertainty (see **Table 3** for exact language). The green highlighted text is not included in the version without the margin of error.

Figure 1. Plain language summary using “colloquial” language for the overall uncertainty and including the margin of error*

What are the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting Covid?

What is the benefit?

Wearing glasses may reduce your chance of getting Covid a little – but we are not very confident about this.

What are the downsides?

We are somewhat confident that wearing glasses does not cause important harms such as a serious fall due to reduced vision. But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.

What is the evidence?

What was known?

Some researchers thought wearing glasses might protect against Covid infection – but the evidence was limited. A [recent systematic review](#) of studies examined whether eye protection – including glasses - protects against Covid infection. The review found that it might make a difference. But the studies were not [randomized studies](#). This means that the findings might be explained by differences in the people who happened to wear glasses rather than any effect glasses might have.

What’s new?

A [new randomized study](#) has been published. Based on the flip of a coin, about 3800 healthy adults were told either to wear glasses when around others, or not to wear them.

Here’s what happened:

BENEFIT

Over the next 2 weeks, slightly fewer people told to wear glasses tested positive for COVID: 9.6% compared to 11.5% of those told not to wear glasses. That’s a difference of 1.9%.

Accounting for the play of chance (i.e., the [margin of error](#)), glasses might reduce the risk of Covid by as much as 3.9% but might increase it by as much as 0.1%.

DOWNSIDERS

There were no major harms linked to wearing glasses. One person reported a fall due to reduced vision, and about 25 people (0.2%) reported being irritated by foggy glasses, especially when also wearing a face mask.

Keep in mind

Wearing glasses may slightly reduce your chance of getting Covid – but we are not very confident about this. This is because of the wide margin of error and important [study limitations](#):

- *People knew if they were told to wear glasses (i.e., the study was not [blinded](#)). This may have led them to behave differently and do other things (which they were not told to do) that might affect their chance of Covid infection. In fact, we know that people in the glasses group were more likely to wear face masks - which might have reduced Covid risk. Being told to wear glasses also might have affected how often people tested themselves for Covid or reported a positive result.*
- *The results might not [apply](#) to you. Covid infection rates were very high in this trial where 11.5% of people got Covid over 2 weeks, meaning there was a big surge at that time. The difference between wearing and not wearing glasses would be less if Covid levels are lower where you are than in this trial.*
- *Some people who were meant to wear glasses didn't (or wore them inconsistently or for less than 2 weeks), and some told not to wear glasses wore them anyway. The effect of glasses might be bigger than what the study found for people who wear glasses consistently compared to not wearing glasses at all.*

What to do?

It's reasonable to try glasses to protect against Covid: there may be some benefit and there are no obvious important harms. So, you might choose to wear glasses if Covid levels are high like in this trial, you are a more cautious person, or you are at more risk of developing serious illness from Covid.

You might choose not to if these do not apply, if glasses are uncomfortable or interfere with mask use, or if you simply don't have access to them.

* The yellow highlighted text differs across the three versions of communicating the overall uncertainty. The green highlighted text is only included in the version with the margin of error.

The three ways of communicating the overall uncertainty are shown in **Table 3**. The same “Keep in mind” text (yellow highlighted in **Figure 1**) is included in both the “GRADE” and “Colloquial” versions

but not in the “Not reported” version. Although the overall uncertainty is not explicitly reported in the “Not reported” version, the adverbs “may” for the benefit (“may reduce”) and “probably” for the downsides (“probably does not increase”) are used in all three versions.

Table 3. Three ways of communicating the overall uncertainty

	What are the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID?
“GRADE”	<p>What is the benefit? Wearing glasses may slightly reduce your chance of getting COVID (⊕⊕○○ low certainty evidence).</p> <p>What are the downsides? Wearing glasses probably does not increase your chance of any major harms, such as a serious fall due to reduced vision (⊕⊕⊕○ moderate certainty evidence). But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.</p>
“Colloquial”	<p>What is the benefit? Wearing glasses may reduce your chance of getting COVID a little – but we are not very confident about this.</p> <p>What are the downsides? We are somewhat confident that wearing glasses does not cause important harms such as a serious fall due to reduced vision. But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.</p>
Not reported	<p>What is the benefit? Wearing glasses may reduce your chance of getting COVID a little.</p> <p>What are the downsides? Wearing glasses probably does not cause important harms such as a serious fall due to reduced vision. But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.</p>

In this study, we are summarizing the results of a trial where the *benefit* of glasses is considered “low certainty” and “less important”; the *harms* are considered “moderate certainty” and “no important harm”. The complete set of “GRADE” and “colloquial” language for communicating the overall uncertainty (for four levels of certainty and three categories of effect sizes) is shown in **Appendix 4**.

The GRADE version includes symbols for the certainty of the evidence, e.g.,

Wearing glasses may slightly reduce your chance of getting COVID (⊕⊕○○ [low certainty evidence](#)).

With hover-over definitions, e.g.,

Low certainty of the evidence means that the likelihood is high that the effect will be different enough from what the research found that it might affect a decision.

and a link to a fuller explanation with all four categories of certainty:

Assessment of the certainty of the evidence*	Definitions
High ⊕⊕⊕⊕	This research provides a very good indication of the likely effect. The likelihood that the effect will be substantially different† is low.
Moderate ⊕⊕⊕○	This research provides a good indication of the likely effect. The likelihood that the effect will be substantially different† is moderate.

Low ⊕⊕○○	This research provides some indication of the likely effect. However, the likelihood that it will be substantially different† is high.
Very low ⊕○○○	This research does not provide a reliable indication of the likely effect. The likelihood that the effect will be substantially different† is very high.

† *Substantially different = a large enough difference that it might affect a decision.*

* Certainty of the evidence is an assessment of the likelihood that the effect will not be substantially different from what the research found, i.e., different enough that it might affect a decision. The reasons for assessing the evidence of the effect of wearing glasses on your chance of getting Covid as “low certainty” is explained under “Keep in mind”.

The two alternatives for the margin of error (confidence interval) are shown in **Table 4**. The “reported” version includes a hover over definition (“The margin of error or ‘confidence interval’ reflects the extent to which the play of chance may be responsible for a result from a study”) which also links to the GET-IT Glossary- Plain language definitions of health research (<https://getitglossary.org/term/confidence+interval>). In the “not reported” version, the wide margin of error is not included as a reason for “low certainty” in the “GRADE” version or saying, “we are not very confident” in the “colloquial” version under “Keep in mind” (**Figure 1**).

Table 4. Two alternatives for the margin of error

	Here’s what happened:
Reported	Over the next 2 weeks, slightly fewer people told to wear glasses tested positive for COVID: 9.6% compared to 11.5% of those told not to wear glasses. That’s a difference of 1.9%. Accounting for the play of chance (i.e., the margin of error), glasses might <i>reduce</i> the risk of COVID by as much as 3.9% but might <i>increase</i> it by as much as 0.1%.
Not reported	Over the next 2 weeks, slightly fewer people told to wear glasses tested positive for COVID: 9.6% compared to 11.5% of those told not to wear glasses. That’s a difference of 1.9%.

User testing of the summaries

We will user test the summaries and the questions that we will ask participants prior to testing the effects of the summaries (**Appendix 2**). If needed, we will modify the text to ensure that they are understood. Briefly, we will gather feedback on the certainty statements and text related to communicating margins of error, on the full public health message text, and on all materials related to the process of participating in the randomized trial (e.g., from invitation to participate to finishing the trial).

With the user test, our objectives are specifically to examine the user experience of the language and format of the text:

- Do the instructions contain the necessary information for stakeholders to understand the questions being asked?
- Does the public health message text contain the necessary information for stakeholders to understand the questions being asked?
- Is the text formatted so that stakeholders can easily find the most important information?

- Can stakeholders easily access more information if needed (e.g., explanations and/or examples related to terms or concepts)
- Is the text formatted so that it is perceived as reliable, easy to understand?
- Does the text facilitate stakeholders' perceptions that they are the intended target audience for the text?

Outcomes

We define three binary co-primary outcomes to measure understanding of overall uncertainty and one to measure understanding of statistical uncertainty (precision of the effect estimate for the benefit). Each of the three outcomes for overall uncertainty will be measured by comparing participants' answers to questions about uncertainty to expected (correct) answers, based on the size of the effects and the certainty of the evidence (**Table 5**). There are two 2-part questions designed to assess understanding of the potential benefit and harm of wearing glasses to reduce COVID risk, and one about the overall information available. The 2-part questions first ask the respondent to (qualitatively) estimate the effect of wearing glasses on the risk of COVID infection. Then he or she is asked to rate how sure they are about their answer.

Understanding of statistical uncertainty will be measured with a single question comparing the participants' answers to the expected answer based on the confidence interval (margin of error) for the effect estimate for benefit. This outcome measure will only be used to compare the three versions that include the margin of error to the three versions that do not.

Table 5. Primary outcome measures

Question	Responses	Expected (correct) answer
<i>Benefit</i>		
What is the effect of wearing glasses on your chance of getting COVID?		
<i>Certainty about benefit</i>		
How sure are you about the effect of wearing glasses on your chance of getting COVID?	Very sure Somewhat sure Somewhat unsure Very unsure	Somewhat unsure
<i>Harm</i>		
How likely do you think it is that wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID can cause any important harms?		
<i>Certainty about harm</i>		
Wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID does <u>not</u> cause important harms	Very sure Somewhat sure Somewhat unsure Very unsure	Somewhat sure
<i>Sufficiency of what is known</i>		
<u>Not enough is known</u> to be sure about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.	Strongly agree Agree Disagree Strongly disagree	Agree or Strongly agree

Question	Responses	Expected (correct) answer
<i>Additional co-primary outcome for comparing including versus not including the margin of error</i>		
Which of the following statements is most consistent with the information provided? Wearing glasses may...	Reduce the chance of COVID a little but might reduce it a lot Reduce the chance of COVID a little, but may have no effect Reduce the chance of COVID a little, but might increase it a little Increase the chance of COVID it a little, but might increase it a lot Don't know	Reduce the chance of COVID a little, but might increase it a little

Secondary outcomes include questions about:

- the perceived benefit and harm of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of COVID infections,
- intended behaviour (whether participants would wear glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID in areas with high and low COVID infection rates),
- perceptions of the trustworthiness, adequacy, clarity, and helpfulness of the information, and likelihood of sharing it with others
- decisional conflict²³

The questions for these outcomes are shown in **Table 6** and **Appendix 5**. The complete set of questions, including the primary outcomes, are shown in the order that they will be asked in **Appendix 6**.

Table 6. Secondary outcome measures

Outcome measure	Response options	
Perceived benefit and harm		
1. What is the effect of wearing glasses is on your chance of getting COVID?	Lowers chance a little	Any other response
2. How likely do you think it is that wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID can cause any important harms?	Unlikely	Any other response
Intended behaviour		
3. If there were a surge of COVID cases in your area, how likely would you be to wear glasses or recommend wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID?	Very likely or Likely	Very unlikely or Unlikely
4. If there were very few COVID cases in your area, how likely would you be to wear glasses or recommend wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID?	Very likely or Likely	Very unlikely or Unlikely
Perceptions of the information		
5. This information is a trustworthy summary of what is known about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.	Strongly agree or Agree	Strongly disagree or Disagree
6. This information is a sufficient summary of what is known about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.	Strongly agree or Agree	Strongly disagree or Disagree
7. I think the information about whether wearing glasses affects the chance of getting COVID was	Very clear or Clear	Very unclear or Unclear
8. I think the information about whether wearing glasses to prevent COVID has important harms was	Very clear or Clear	Very unclear or Unclear
9. Overall, I think the information about wearing glasses to prevent COVID was	Very helpful or Helpful	Very unhelpful or Unhelpful
10. Say you knew someone who heard that wearing glasses might affect your chance of getting COVID. How likely would you be to share the information you just saw with them?	Definitely yes or Probably yes	Definitely no or Probably no

Outcome measure	Response options	
Decisional conflict		
11. The decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID cases was hard for me to make.	Strongly agree or Agree	Strongly disagree or Disagree
12. I feel I made an informed decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID.	Strongly agree or Agree	Strongly disagree or Disagree
13. I am satisfied with my decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID.	Strongly agree or Agree	Strongly disagree or Disagree

Statistical analysis

We will conduct two separate trials: one using Prolific and one using SurveyMonkey Audience. This will enable us to compare the two platforms and the results of the two trials. We will combine the effect estimates for the two trials using the Mantel-Haenzel fixed effect method and test for subgroup differences between the results of the trials using Prolific and the trial using SurveyMonkey Audience.

For each trial, we will use logistic regression to estimate odds ratios for the main effects (presenting overall uncertainty or presenting margin of error), and the associated interaction effects, for each of the three co-primary outcomes for understanding overall uncertainty and for the additional co-primary outcome for understanding statistical uncertainty (**Table 7**). We will define the reference levels of the treatment variables to be no presentation of uncertainty and no presentation of margin of error. We hypothesise that fewer participants will understand uncertainty if no uncertainty is presented compared to the other treatment combinations. To aid interpretation of results for each co-primary outcome, we will re-express the estimated quantities as differences compared to the reference treatment (positive differences will indicate a higher probability of understanding uncertainty; **Table 8**). We will also compare the primary outcome results in the colloquial vs. GRADE groups.

We will report 95% confidence intervals and two-sided *p*-values, where applicable, throughout. We will explore numeracy, salience, and country (see Covariates below) as potential effect modifiers. We hypothesise that participants who are more numerate will be more likely to correctly understand uncertainty. We do not have a priori hypotheses for salience or country.

Table 7. Odds ratios for each of the co-primary outcomes for understanding of overall uncertainty for benefit, harm, and sufficiency of what is known

	Odds Ratio [95% CI]			<i>p</i> -values		
	Benefit	Harm	Sufficiency	Benefit	Harm	Sufficiency
Main Effects						
Colloquial	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	0.XXX	0.XXX	0.XXX
GRADE	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	0.XXX	0.XXX	0.XXX
Margin of Error	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	0.XXX	0.XXX	0.XXX
Interactions						
Colloquial × Margin of Error	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	0.XXX	0.XXX	0.XXX
GRADE × Margin of Error	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	XXX [XXX-XXX]	0.XXX	0.XXX	0.XXX

The reference treatment is no presentation of uncertainty and no presentation of margin of error.

Table 8. Differences for each of the co-primary outcomes for understanding of overall uncertainty for benefit, harm, and sufficiency of what is known

Uncertainty	Margin of Error	Benefit		Harm		Sufficiency	
		Participants ¹	Diff. (%) ²	Participants ¹	Diff. (%) ²	Participants ¹	Diff. (%) ²
None	No	n/N (XXX%)	0	n/N (XXX%)	0	n/N (XXX%)	0
Colloquial	No	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]
GRADE	No	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]
None	Yes	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]
Colloquial	Yes	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]
GRADE	Yes	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	n/N (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]

1. Data are number of participants who understand the uncertainty, the number of participants randomized to the treatment (and percentage). 2. Estimates of odds ratios (Table 7) have been re-expressed as risk differences (with 95% confidence intervals). A positive difference indicates a higher probability of understanding uncertainty compared to the reference treatment (no presentation of uncertainty and no presentation of margin of error).

We will analyse additional co-primary outcome for understanding of statistical uncertainty and the secondary outcomes using the same approach as for the co-primary outcomes for understanding of overall uncertainty, using the dichotomizations shown in Table 6. We will report a selection of the secondary outcomes in the main text (Table 9 shows an example for the first secondary outcome). The others will be reported in supplementary materials.

Table 9. Results for the secondary outcome: What is the effect of wearing glasses is on your chance of getting COVID?

Overall uncertainty	Margin of Error	N ¹	Lowers the chance a little ²	Any other response ²	Diff. (%) ³	Odds Ratio ⁴	p-value
None	No	XXX	n (XXX%)	n (XXX%)	0	1	NA
Colloquial	No	XXX	n (XXX%)	n (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX
GRADE	No	XXX	n (XXX%)	n (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX
None	Yes	XXX	n (XXX%)	n (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX
Colloquial	Yes	XXX	n (XXX%)	n (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX
GRADE	Yes	XXX	n (XXX%)	n (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX

Data are numbers of participants randomized¹ and numbers providing each of the two responses². Estimates of odds ratios⁴ have been re-expressed as risk differences³ (each with 95% confidence intervals). Positive risk differences and odds ratios greater than 1 indicate a higher probability of replying "Lowers the chance a little".. The reference treatment is no presentation of uncertainty and no presentation of margin of error.

We will follow the intention-to-treat principle in all analyses: all participants will be included and analysed in the arms to which they were randomized. If complete-case data are missing for more than 5% of randomized participants, we will investigate possible explanations for the missingness.²⁴ If data cannot plausibly be explained as being missing completely at random (MCAR), we will perform analyses using multiple imputation by chained equations using the covariates as auxiliary

variables.²⁵ Statistical analyses will be performed using Stata version 16 or later (StataCorp LLC, College Station, Texas, USA). Anonymized individual-level data and analysis code will be made publicly available.

Power calculation

We do not have *a priori* information about the relative effectiveness of the various ways of communicating information about uncertainty, nor how they may interact, and have a limited understanding for what may constitute an important effect. We used an informal consensus-based approach to propose probabilities that participants would understand uncertainty under each of the six conditions. These ranged from 35% of participants understanding uncertainty if no overall uncertainty and no margin of error are presented, to 75% of participants if GRADE language is used (whether a margin of error is presented or not). We used simulation to estimate the minimum number of participants who should be randomized to detect all main and interaction effects at the 95% significance level with 90% power. Based on the assumptions above, we estimate that the study should randomize at least 396 participants (66 participants for each of the six comparison groups), not accounting for any losses. Given these uncertainties, we will aim to recruit 480 participants (80 per group).

Covariates

We have identified three covariates that could potentially modify the effects of the different ways of communicating uncertainty (see also Potential effect modifiers, below): numeracy, salience, and country (Norway or USA). Numeracy will be assessed using a validated instrument (**Table 10**) with a pre-specified cut-off of 3 vs. <3 points on the 0-3 scale.²⁶

Table 10. The 3-item numeracy assessment scale²⁶

Task	Question
Convert a percent to a proportion	A person taking Drug A has a 1% chance of having an allergic reaction. If 1,000 people take Drug A, how many would you expect to have an allergic reaction? ___ person(s) out of 1,000
Convert a proportion to a percent	A person taking Drug B has a 1 in 1,000 chance of an allergic reaction. What percent of people taking Drug B will have an allergic reaction? ___ %
Basic probability	Imagine that you flip a coin 1,000 times. What is your best guess about how many times the coin would come up heads in 1,000 flips? ___times out of 1,000

We will use two questions to assess salience (i.e., how relevant or important the hypothetical scenario is to participants): how worried they are about getting COVID and how important it is to them to take actions to reduce their chance of getting COVID (**Appendix 5**). We will dichotomise

salience as “salient” (very or extremely worried and very or extremely important) or “not salient” (any other combination of responses).

Potential effect modifiers

We will perform subgroup analyses to explore whether each of the three covariates may be an effect modifier for each of the three co-primary outcomes. We do not have *a priori* hypotheses about how these factors might modify the effects. For a given outcome and potential effect modifier, we will estimate main and interaction effects, as described above, on subgroups defined by the levels of the potential effect modifier. We will present the estimated odds ratios using one forest plot for each of the co-primary outcomes and will present *p*-values testing null hypotheses of homogeneity (i.e., no effect modification) for each subgroup, but we will be cautious when interpreting these analyses. Finally, we will assess the credibility of subgroup differences (potential effect modification) using the Instrument to assess the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN).²⁷

Ethical considerations

This study was considered for ethical approval by the Regional Ethics Committee for South-East Norway and was found not to require ethical approval since it falls outside the Committees mandate under the Health Research Act (reference 557972).

[SW- add CPHS when available](#)

Participants must be 18 years-old or older. Everyone invited to participate will be given information about who is doing the research, the goal, what they will be asked to do, and the risks and benefits of participating (**Appendix 7**). Before being randomized, they will need to provide written consent electronically. The collected data will be anonymous, and it will not be possible to trace back to the participants. Participation is voluntary, participants can discontinue participation at any time, and they can contact the investigators if they have any questions or concerns.

Competing interests

None declared.

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Protocol registration

This protocol is in the process of being registered in ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT# pending) and is posted on ZENOVO (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7334968>).

Protocol amendments

All protocol amendments will be numbered sequentially, dated, and recorded in the protocol and ClinicalTrials.gov.

Authors' contributions

SW prepared the first draft of this protocol. CJR provided statistical expertise. All the authors read, provided feedback, and approved the final manuscript. SW is the guarantor.

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Appendices

1. A public health messages laboratory
2. Protocol for examining user experience
3. The six plain language summaries
4. "GRADE" and "colloquial" language for communicating overall uncertainty
5. Secondary outcome measures, demographic data, and potential effect modifiers
6. Questionnaire
7. Consent form (for questionnaire)

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